

From Acceptance to Continuance: Investigating Trust and Privacy Risk in Mandatory AI-Based Biometric Boarding Systems at Indonesian Railways

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Abstract. The rise of Automated Biometric Boarding Systems (ABBS) for public transportation, driven by the potential to enrich convenience while integrating artificial intelligence into their activities has not been without the desire among policymakers and business leaders to get a better grasp on how biometry could be integrated in mandatory adoption contexts. Abstract This study aims to investigate passenger acceptance and continuance intention of AI-based face recognition boarding system in PT Kereta Api Indonesia (KAI) Gambir Railway Station 2023. Based on an integrated framework of Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Expectation-Confirmation Model (ECM), complemented with Trust and Perceived Privacy Risk, this study explores the pathways through which affective factors and institutional factors influence long-term behavioral intentions in a compulsory acceptance context. Data from cross-sectional, quantitative. 150 purposively sampled passengers were analyzed by PLS-SEM using SmartPLS 4.0. This is the first time that these findings challenge many of the assumptions about technology adoption and provide relevant policy recommendations for transport authorities based on a framework for AI governance aligned with Indonesia's Personal Data Protection Law (UU No. 27/2022).

Keywords: Technology Acceptance Model, Artificial Intelligence, Biometric Boarding.

1 Introduction

The railway network of Indonesia is a vital transport artery, with Gambir Railway Station in Central Jakarta handling hundreds of thousands of passengers every day. Typically, the boarding procedure consists of station officers physically checking tickets together with identity documents before allowing passengers access through the gate, leading to congestion in peak times and possibilities for human error and identity fraud.

In an effort to overcome these operational obstacles, PT Kereta Api Indonesia (KAI) applied an AI-based face recognition boarding system at Gambir Station in 2023. This multimodal biometric system cuts down verification time to seconds by automatically matching live facial scans with identity databases, allowing contactless access, and preventing the need for queuing up before boarding.

Though these operational advantages are significant, what actually keeps the system going over time is not superficial acceptance but also continuance intention: a motivation to keep using the system after adoption. Bhattacharjee's Expectation-Confirmation Model (ECM) [5] suggests users evaluate their experience using the system, leading to satisfaction, which then influences continued use. More concerns arise due to the extensive data collected as part of the system implementation (i.e., immutable biometric data, facial features), raising significant

privacy issues under Indonesia's Personal Data Protection Law—Undang-Undang No. 27 Tahun 2022—which makes Trust and Perceived Privacy Risk especially relevant considerations for adoption.

This paper identifies the basic factors affecting passengers' acceptance and continuance intention on the KAI biometric boarding system, extending the TAM-ECM [5] framework with Trust and Perceived Privacy Risk. Data from 150 purposively sampled passengers were analyzed using PLS-SEM (SmartPLS 4.0). This study contributes to the literature on biometric technology adoption in public transport while providing KAI with tangible data that may assist in devising strategies to improve passenger acceptance as part of Indonesia's smart railway ecosystem.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Continuance Intention and Technology Acceptance Model

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) postulated by Davis [1] delineates two beliefs affecting individual adoption and use of technology: (1) Perceived Usefulness (PU), defined as “the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance” [2]; and (2) Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU), defined as “the degree to which a person believes that using a given system would be effort-free.” These beliefs impact Attitude Towards Using (ATU) the technology and consequently behavioral intention.

In this study, PU is defined by the belief that face recognition is functionally beneficial for passengers (e.g., faster boarding, no physical documents needed) as opposed to manual verification. PEOU encompasses the non-contactability of facial scanning. Hypotheses H1 to H4 form the basis for how ATU completely mediates the relationship between TAM beliefs and behavioral intention, as confirmed by Taylor and Todd [4].

The ECM [5] developed by Bhattacharjee is a post-adoption behavioral theory describing how users review their actual usage experiences against prior expectations. Post-adoption confirmation of expectations is positively related to Perceived Usefulness, which ultimately affects Overall Satisfaction (OS). Satisfied users are therefore more likely to exhibit Continuance Intention. Hypotheses H5 and H6 emerged from integrating TAM and ECM to reveal insights about both initial acceptance and post-adoption behaviour.

2.2 Trust

Trust (TR) refers to passengers' trust in the accuracy of the face recognition technology and the institutional integrity of KAI as the operating entity [9]. Trust involves expectations of systemic competence (accurate identity authentication), benevolence (KAI acting in the interests of its passengers), and integrity (KAI keeping publicly proclaimed data promises). To ensure passengers continue providing their facial biometric data, they need assurance that this most sensitive personal information is being secured properly, processed reliably, and not misused or disseminated without consent.

In contexts of uncertainty and risk that characterize sensitive personal data processing [10], trust is a crucial factor enabling system functionality. Through KAI being a state-owned enterprise accountable to Indonesia's Personal Data Protection Law, institutional trust is central. Prior research by Wang et al. [10] showed that institutional trust mechanisms are

among the strongest predictors of technology continuance. Accordingly, this study proposes that Trust has an indirect effect on Continuance Intention (H7) and increases Perceived Privacy Risk (H8), as Trust influences cognitive processing of privacy risks by users.

2.3 Perceived Privacy Risk

Perceived Privacy Risk (PPR) is defined as a consumer’s estimation of the chance and associated impact in losing control over personal information through the use of technology [11]. Facial biometric data, unlike conventional authentication credentials like passwords or PINs, is intrinsically tied to an individual—it cannot be changed or revoked once compromised. This fixed nature makes biometric data collection significantly more high-stakes, making PPR a critical construct in this research context.

Usability aspects alone are not a strong enough barrier to user acceptance as privacy concerns do much heavier lifting against unauthorized third-party access, compromised systems, and secondary sharing [12, 13]. PPR is defined as the anxiety perceived by passengers toward KAI’s collection, storage, processing, and sharing of facial data. Conventional technology adoption models posit that as perception of risk increases, usage will decrease (H9 conventional direction), but this study hypothesizes and tests that this is not necessarily the case for a mandatory biometric context.

2.4 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual model consists of seven constructs: Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, Attitude Toward Using, Overall Satisfaction, Continuance Intention, Trust, and Perceived Privacy Risk. The theory-based practical routes include the PU and PEOU to ATU pathway (utility-belief route) derived from core TAM, and the PU to OS to CI satisfaction path which drives ECM, while Trust and PPR correlate with fundamental socio-technical aspects of the biometric data processing cycle. This framework provides the basis for nine hypotheses illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework: Integrated TAM-ECM with Trust and Perceived Privacy Risk

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3 Methodology

3.1 Research Design and Approach

This study takes a cross-sectional survey design. The quantitative paradigm was chosen because specific constructs were to be measured as part of the research objectives and

directional relationships had been established through statistical inference. The structured questionnaire standardizes responses among respondents, offering a reproducible approach. This design was also suitable since after adoption, users capture their current perceptions and intentions at a single point in time.

3.2 Population, Sampling, and Data Collection

The respondents of this study were passengers using the AI-based face recognition boarding gate directly at Gambir Railway Station. To embed perception in real rather than imaginary experience, only passengers who had already passed through the biometric gate at least once were included. Purposive (judgment) sampling was used to include only informants with first-hand experience of the system. Data were collected through a self-administered online questionnaire using Google Forms over four weeks. A survey link was circulated in the Gambir Station boarding gate area and through social media communities of regular Gambir users. Out of 162 responses received, 12 were excluded due to incomplete answers or failure to meet the experiential inclusion criterion, leaving N=150 usable responses. This sample size meets the recommended minimum requirements for PLS-SEM with seven predictors (minimum $n = 100$ per Hair et al. [7]) and is statistically powerful enough for bootstrapping.

3.3 Questionnaire Development and Measurement

Two parts were included in the survey instrument. Section A captured demographic data (gender, age, profession, travel frequency, and prior familiarity with face recognition). Section B operationalized seven latent constructs using validated indicator scales adapted from the literature. PU and PEOU were assessed by four items each (adapted from [1]). OS and CI were adapted from Bhattacharjee [5] (four items each), and ATU items were adapted from Taylor and Todd [4]. TR was operationalized following Gefen [9]; PPR was adapted from Featherman et al. [8], also with four items. All indicators were measured on a five-point Likert-type response scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree). For content validity, item wording was contextualized for AI-based biometric boarding at Gambir Station. Two academics with backgrounds in information systems and tourism management reviewed the questionnaire before deployment and suggested minor wording changes.

3.4 Analytical Method: PLS-SEM

Data were analyzed via PLS-SEM using SmartPLS 4.0. The suitability of PLS-SEM compared to covariance-based SEM (CB-SEM) was threefold: (1) PLS handles small sample sizes better and accommodates non-normal data distributions; (2) PLS is more suited for exploratory or predictive research aiming to maximize explained variance in endogenous constructs; and (3) the composite theoretical framework marks a departure from purely confirmatory, factor-based approaches [7, 14].

Analysis proceeded in two stages following Hair et al. [7]. Stage 1 assessed the measurement model for convergent validity (outer loadings ≥ 0.70 , AVE ≥ 0.50), discriminant validity (Fornell-Larcker criterion and HTMT ratio < 0.85), and internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability ≥ 0.70). Stage 2 tested structural model hypotheses using bootstrapping with 5,000 resamples at $\alpha = 0.05$ ($t > 1.96$). Mediation was assessed using percentile bootstrapping confidence intervals.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Respondent Profile and Descriptive Statistics

Of 150 respondents, 55.3% were male and 44.7% female. The most represented age group was 17–25 years (28.0%), followed by ≥ 46 years (26.7%), 26–35 years (25.3%), and 36–45 years (20.0%). By occupation, private-sector employees constituted the majority (50.0%), followed by government/military/SOE employees (19.3%), entrepreneurs (15.3%), and students (15.3%). Most respondents had transited Gambir 1–2 times (55.3%), then 3–5 times (34.7%), and more than five times (10.0%). All 150 respondents (100%) reported prior experience with facial recognition technology. Full demographic details are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Respondent Demographic Profile.

Characteristic	Category	N	%
Gender	Male	83	55.3%
	Female	67	44.7%
Age	17-25 years	42	28.0%
	26-35 years	38	25.3%
	36-45 years	30	20.0%
	≥ 46 years	40	26.7%
Occupation	Private-sector employee	75	50.0%
	Gov./Military/SOE employee	29	19.3%
	Entrepreneur	23	15.3%
	Student	23	15.3%
Travel Frequency	1-2 times	83	55.3%
	3-5 times	52	34.7%
	>5 times	15	10.0%
Prior FR Experience	Yes	150	100%

Table 2 presents descriptive statistics for all seven constructs. Mean scores are in the mid-to-upper range of the 5-point scale (CI: 3.297–TR: 3.392), indicating a moderate-to-favorable response tendency. Standard deviations ranged from 1.167 (PEOU) to 1.220 (PPR), and Coefficients of Variation ranged from 34.5% to 36.3%, showing similar variability across constructs. The mean for CI was lowest (3.297) and TR highest (3.392), demonstrating that passengers evince somewhat more institutional trust than intention to continue.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of Constructs.

Construct	Mean	Median	Mode	SD	Variance	CV (%)
PU	3.340	3.250	3.000	1.182	1.397	35.4
PEOU	3.382	3.750	4.000	1.167	1.363	34.5
ATU	3.377	3.500	5.000	1.207	1.458	35.8
OS	3.365	3.500	5.000	1.195	1.428	35.5
CI	3.297	3.500	4.000	1.187	1.409	36.0
PPR	3.358	3.500	4.000	1.220	1.489	36.3
TR	3.392	3.500	4.000	1.174	1.379	34.6

Note: All constructs measured on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree; 5 = Strongly Agree). SD = Standard Deviation; CV = Coefficient of Variation ($SD/Mean \times 100$).

4.2 Measurement Model Assessment

All measurement model results are summarized in Table 3. Convergent validity was established with outer loadings ranging from 0.684 (PU1, slightly below the 0.70 threshold but retained [7]) to 0.891 (PEOU2), and all AVE values exceeding 0.50 (range: 0.646–0.686). PU1 was retained as its removal did not substantially alter AVE and preserved content validity of the PU construct as originally operationalized by Davis [1]. Discriminant validity was confirmed via the Fornell-Larcker criterion (Table 4; all diagonal \sqrt{AVE} values exceeded inter-construct correlations) and HTMT ratios (all < 0.85 ; highest PPR to CI = 0.605). Internal consistency was acceptable across all constructs (alpha: 0.827–0.849; CR pa: 0.831–0.892; CR pc: 0.879–0.897). All outer model indicator VIF values were below 5.0 (range: 1.622–2.284) and inner model VIFs were below 1.10, confirming absence of multicollinearity.

Table 3. Measurement Model: Reliability, AVE, R², and Effect Size (f²→CI).

Construct	alpha	CR (pa)	CR (pc)	AVE	R ²	R ² adj	f ² ->CI
ATU	0.849	0.863	0.897	0.686	0.029	0.015	0.189
CI	0.845	0.848	0.896	0.683	0.533	0.520	--
OS	0.846	0.856	0.896	0.684	0.009	0.002	0.159
PEOU	0.843	0.892	0.893	0.676	--	--	--
PPR	0.841	0.850	0.894	0.678	0.099	0.093	0.249
PU	0.839	0.832	0.879	0.646	0.006	-0.001	--
TR	0.827	0.831	0.885	0.658	--	--	0.165

Note: alpha = Cronbach's Alpha; CR (pa/pc) = Composite Reliability; AVE = Average Variance Extracted; f²->CI = Cohen's f² effect size for direct path to Continuance Intention. Thresholds: alpha/CR > 0.70 [7]; AVE > 0.50 [7]. R² interpretation: > 0.67 Substantial, 0.33–0.67 Moderate, 0.19–0.33 Weak [7]. -- = exogenous construct or no direct path to CI.

Table 4. Fornell-Larcker Criterion (Discriminant Validity).

	ATU	CI	OS	PEOU	PPR	PU	TR
ATU	0.828						
CI	0.422	0.826					
OS	0.184	0.343	0.827				
PEOU	-0.145	0.299	0.142	0.822			
PPR	0.115	0.513	0.080	-0.049	0.824		
PU	0.099	0.273	-0.094	-0.078	-0.018	0.804	
TR	0.082	0.414	-0.072	0.026	0.314	0.003	0.811

Note: Diagonal values = \sqrt{AVE} . Off-diagonal = inter-construct Pearson correlations. Discriminant validity confirmed when diagonal exceeds all values in same row and column [7].

4.3 Structural Model and Hypothesis Testing

Results of the full hypothesis test are presented in Table 5. Five out of nine proposed hypotheses were supported. The structural model showed moderate-to-high predictive power for Continuance Intention ($R^2 = 0.533$, $R^2_{adj} = 0.520$). R^2 values for all other endogenous constructs were small (ATU = 0.029; OS = 0.009; PPR = 0.099), resulting in non-significant TAM pathways (all $p > 0.166$). Model fit indices were SRMR = 0.061 (saturated model) / 0.095 (estimated model), NFI = 0.764.

Table 5. Hypothesis Testing Results (Bootstrapping, 5,000 Resamples, Two-Tailed).

H	Relationship	Beta	t-stat	p	95% CI	Result
H1	PU -> ATU	0.088	0.792	0.428	[-0.165, 0.265]	Not Supported
H2	PEOU -> ATU	-0.138	1.385	0.166	[-0.302, 0.108]	Not Supported
H3	PEOU -> PU	-0.078	0.623	0.533	[-0.265, 0.198]	Not Supported
H4	ATU -> CI	0.305	5.127	<0.001	[0.187, 0.417]	Supported
H5	PU -> OS	-0.094	0.913	0.361	[-0.273, 0.129]	Not Supported
H6	OS -> CI	0.279	4.518	<0.001	[0.161, 0.403]	Supported
H7	TR -> CI	0.295	4.977	<0.001	[0.184, 0.416]	Supported
H8	TR -> PPR	0.314	4.106	<0.001	[0.169, 0.471]	Supported
H9	PPR -> CI	0.363	5.777	<0.001	[0.239, 0.484]	Supported

Note: Significance at $p < 0.05$ ($t > 1.96$). 95% CI from percentile bootstrapping (SmartPLS 4.0).

4.4 Discussion

PPR to CI (H9, $\beta = 0.363$, $f^2 = 0.249$, Supported). Perceived Privacy Risk emerged as the strongest predictor of Continuance Intention with a counterintuitive positive effect: greater privacy risk awareness was associated with stronger rather than weaker continuance intention, contrary to the typical assumption in TAM and privacy calculus models [11, 13]. Under the passive biometric system at Gambir Station, passengers have no mechanism to bypass the verification process. This structural compulsion produces a form of learned helplessness [15]: users persist through privacy concerns because behavioral avoidance is infeasible. An additional interpretation involves a pragmatic risk-benefit trade-off where the convenience of contactless rapid boarding coexists with but does not eliminate privacy concerns. This aligns with Kokolakis [15] and necessitates reconsideration of PPR significance in mandatory adoption contexts.

ATU to CI (H4, $\beta = 0.305$, $f^2 = 0.189$, Supported). In line with central TAM, attitudes toward the biometric system had a strong impact on intention to use. Importantly, ATU maintained a significant relationship with intention in the absence of PU and PEOU as antecedents, suggesting that within forced settings attitude is based on trust or obligation instead of utility or usability.

TR to CI (H7, $\beta = 0.295$, $f^2 = 0.165$, Supported). Institutional trust in KAI is a substantial factor predicting Continuance Intention. Facial biometric data is non-revocable once lost, making institutional trust all the more important. Passengers must believe that KAI practices true responsible data stewardship in accordance with UU No. 27/2022; legal compliance alone is insufficient [9, 10], and trust is predicated on perceived integrity and benevolence.

OS to CI (H6, $\beta = 0.279$, $f^2 = 0.159$, Supported). Consistent with ECM [5], Overall Satisfaction was determinative for CI. The non-significance of the PU to OS path further establishes that satisfaction is largely derived from a better boarding experience and was less related to narrowly defined functional utilities. Experiential elements such as staff behavior, clarity of signage, gate responsiveness, and overall boarding atmosphere matter much more in driving satisfaction than the mere usefulness of the technology.

TR to PPR (H8, $\beta = 0.314$, Supported) and Indirect Effect. The positive coefficient for trust on Perceived Privacy Risk means that trust does not reduce privacy risk perception but instead coexists with and even increases privacy awareness. Trust in KAI makes passengers more cognitively alert to the privacy implications of biometric data collection, consistent with Dinev and Hart [16] showing that trust and risk perception co-exist among privacy-literate populations. Trust's total effect on continuance via two pathways (direct: 0.295; indirect through privacy awareness: 0.114; total: 0.409) represents the strongest model-level influence on continued use.

Non-supported hypotheses (H1, H2, H3, H5) consistently contradict the classical TAM framework and are theoretically interpretable through the mandatory adoption lens [14]: when technology use is compulsory rather than discretionary, utilitarian evaluations (usefulness and ease of use) decouple from attitude formation and satisfaction judgments. The negative albeit non-significant PEOU coefficient hints at a ceiling effect, as passengers may already perceive the system as sufficiently easy to use.

In theory, this study demonstrates the collapse of the classical TAM utility-attitude pathway under mandatory conditions for biometric adoption, and that affective constructs (ATU, OS) and socio-technical constructs (TR, PPR) receive primacy. In practice, KAI should direct actions toward: (1) clear proactive messaging on biometric data utilization and compliance with UU No. 27/2022; (2) holistic boarding experience improvement rather than technical capability marketing alone; (3) responsive customer support with privacy governance processes visibly demonstrated; and (4) awareness that while passengers who care about privacy will continue using the system anyway, ignoring privacy concerns can pose a long-term attrition risk if opt-out alternatives are introduced in the future.

5 Conclusion

This research investigated acceptance and Continuance Intention of passengers using the Artificial Intelligence Face Recognition-Based Boarding System at Gambir Railway Station, using an integrated model of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Expectation-Confirmation Model (ECM) extended by Trust and Perceived Privacy Risk. A total of nine hypotheses were developed, five of which were supported based on PLS-SEM analysis of 150 respondents. The most direct influence on Continuance Intention was Perceived Privacy Risk ($\beta = 0.363$), followed by Attitude Toward Using ($\beta = 0.305$), Trust ($\beta = 0.295$), and Overall Satisfaction ($\beta = 0.279$). The model accounted for 53.3% of the variance in CI ($R^2 = 0.533$).

Classical TAM pathways were consistently non-significant (all $p > 0.166$), confirming that affective, evaluative, and trust-based mechanisms govern mandatory biometric technology adoption over utility beliefs. Trust showed the greatest total effect on CI (0.409), comprising a direct effect (0.295) and indirect pathway through Perceived Privacy Risk (0.114). Future work should use longitudinal designs to track trust and perceived privacy over time after adoption, as well as comparative studies across stations and transport modes for generalizability.

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